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Research Article

**PREPARATION AND OPTIMIZATION OF DEFERASIROX
IMMEDIATE RELEASE TABLETS****Mohd Ismail Khalid Hashmi*, Dr.Y.Ganesh Kumar**KVK College of Pharmacy, Surmaiguda (V), Lashkarguda (G.P), Abdullapurmet (M),
Ranga Reddy District**Abstract:**

The objective of this study is to formulate and significantly improve the bioavailability and reduce the side effects of immediate release tablets of Deferasirox. The precompression blends of Deferasirox were characterized with respect to angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index and Hausner's ratio. The precompression blend of all the batches indicates well to fair flowability and compressibility. Immediate release tablets were prepared with various polymers like Croscarmellose sodium, Sodium starch glycolate and Crospovidone at different concentration ratios and were compressed into tablets. The formulated tablets were evaluated for various quality control parameters. The tablets were passed all tests. Among all the formulations F7 formulation containing, drug and Sodium starch glycolate showed good result that is 99.94 % in 45 min. Hence from the dissolution data it was evident that F7 formulation is the better formulation.

Keywords: Deferasirox, Immediate release, Croscarmellose sodium, Sodium starch glycolate, Crospovidone.

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INTRODUCTION:

Oral route is the most convenient and extensively used for drug administration. Oral administration is the most popular route for systemic effects due to its ease of ingestion, pain, avoidance, versatility and most importantly, patient compliance suitable for industrial production, improved stability and bioavailability. The concept of immediate release tablets emerged from the desire to provide patient with more conventional means of taking their medication when emergency treatment is required. Recently, immediate release tablets have gained prominence of being new drug delivery systems. The oral route of administration has so far received the maximum attention with respect to research on physiological and drug constraints as well as design and testing of product, Drug delivery systems are a strategic tool for expanding markets/indications, extending product life cycles and generating opportunities. Most immediate release tablets are intended to disintegrate in the stomach, where the pH is acidic.^[1] Several orally disintegrating tablet technologies based on direct compression. In pharmaceutical formulation includes any formulation in which the rate of release of drug from the formulation is at least 70% (preferably 80%) of active ingredient within 4 hours, such as within 3 hours, preferably 2 hours, more preferably within 1.5 hours, and especially within an hour (such as within 30 minutes) of administration. In Formulation of immediate release the commonly Superdisintegrants used are Croscarmellose, sodium, Sodium Starch glycolate and Crospovidone.^[2]

Immediate release drug delivery is suitable for drugs having long biological half-life, high bioavailability, lower clearance and lower elimination half-life. But main requirement for immediate release dosage form is poor solubility of the drug and need the immediate action of drug to treat undesirable imperfection or disease.^[3]

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials:

Deferasirox was the gift sample from Hetero labs. Hyderabad, India, Croscarmellose sodium from Yarrow Chem. Products, Mumbai, Sodium starch glycolate from S.D Fine Chem. Ltd, Mumbai, Crospovidone procured from S.D Fine Chem. Ltd, Mumbai, Mannitol and MCC Purchased from Yarrow Chem. Products, Mumbai.

Buffer Preparation:

Preparation of 0.2M Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate solution:

Accurately weighed 27.218 gm of monobasic potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate was dissolved in 1000mL of distilled water and mixed.

Preparation of 0.2M sodium hydroxide solution:

Accurately weighed 8gms sodium hydroxide pellets were dissolved 1000ml of distilled water and mixed.

Preparation of pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer:

Accurately measured 250ml of 0.2M potassium Dihydrogen ortho phosphate and 112.5 ml 0.2M NaOH was taken into the 1000ml volumetric flask. Volume was made up to 1000ml with distilled water.

Preformulation Studies:

Preformulation involves the application of biopharmaceutical principles to the physicochemical parameters of drug substance are characterized with the goal of designing optimum drug delivery system.^[4]

Analytical method development for Deferasirox:

a) Determination of absorption maxima:

A spectrum of the working standards was obtained by scanning from 200-400nm against the reagent blank to fix absorption maxima. The λ_{max} was found to be 328 nm. Hence all further investigation was carried out at the same wavelength.

b) Preparation of Standard graph in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer:

100 mg of Deferasirox was dissolved in method 5ml, volumetric flask make up to 100ml of Phosphate beffer of pH 6.8., form primary stock 10ml was transferred to another volumetric flask made up to 100ml with Phosphate buffer of pH 6.8, from this secondary stock was taken separately and made up to 10 ml with Phosphate buffer of pH 6.8, to produce 5,10,15,20 and 25 μ g/ml respectively. The absorbance was measured at 328 nm by using a UV spectrophotometer.^[5]

Formulation Development:

- Drug and different concentrations for super Disintegrates and required ingredients were accurately weighed and passed through a 40-mesh screen to get uniform size particles and mixed in a glass mortar for 15 minutes.
- The obtained blend was lubricated with Magnesium stearate and glidant (Talc) was added and mixing was continued for further 5 minutes.
- The resultant mixture was directly compressed into tablets by using punch of rotary tablet compression machine. Compression force was kept constant for all formulations.^[6,7]

Table 1: Formulations of Immediate Release tablets of Deferasirox

INGREDIENTS	FORMULATIONS											
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Deferasirox	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
CCS	10	20	30	40	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SSG	--	--	--	--	10	20	30	40	--	--	--	--
CP	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	10	20	30	40
Mannitol	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5
MCC	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.
Mg. stearate	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Talc	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Total weight	100	100	100	100.	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

(Total weight of tablet = 100 mg)

Evaluation parameters:

Pre compression parameters:

Measurement of Micromeritic Properties of Powders:^[8,9]

1. Angle of repose: The angle of repose of API powder is determined by the funnel method. The accurately weight powder blend are taken in the funnel. The height of the funnel is adjusted in way that, the tip of the funnel just touched the apex of the powder blend. The powder blend is allowed to flow through the funnel freely on the surface. The diameter of the powder cone is measured and angle of repose is calculated using the following equation.

$$\tan \theta = h/r$$

where, h and r are the height and radius of the powder cone.

2. Bulk density: The powder sample under test is screened through sieve No.18 and the sample equivalent to 25 gm is weighed and filled in a 100 ml graduated cylinder and the power is leveled and the unsettled volume, V_0 is noted. The bulk density is calculated in g/cm^3 by the formula.

$$\text{Bulk density} = M/V_0$$

M= Powder mass

V_0 = apparent unstirred volume

3. Tapped density: The powder sample under test is screened through sieve No.18 and the weight of the sample equivalent to 25 gm filled in 100 ml granulated cylinder. The mechanical tapping of cylinder is carried out using tapped density tester at a nominal rate for 500 times initially and the tapped volume V_0 is noted. Tapping's are preceded further for an additional tapping 750 times and tapped volume, V_b is noted. The difference between two tapping volume is less than 2%, V_b is considered as a tapped volume V_f . The tapped density is calculated in g/cm^3 by the formula.

$$\text{Tapped density} = M/V_f$$

M= weight of sample power taken

V_f = tapped volume

4. Compressibility Index

The Compressibility Index of the power blend is determined by Carr's compressibility index to know the flow character of a powder. The formula for Carr's Index is a below:

$$\text{Carr's Index (\%)} = [(TD-BD)/TD] \times 100$$

5. Hauser's ratio

The Hauser's ratio is a number that is correlated to the flowability of a powder or granular material. The ratio of tapped density to bulk density of the powders is called the Hauser's ratio. It is calculated by the following equation.

$$H = \rho_T / \rho_B$$

Where ρ_T = tapped density, ρ_B = bulk density

Post compression parameters:

a) Thickness: The thickness of tablets was determined by using Digital micrometer. Ten individual tablets from each batch were used and the results averaged.

b) Weight variation: Twenty tablets randomly selected from each batch and individually. Weighed the average weight and standard deviation three batches were calculated. It passes the test weight variation test if not more than two of the individual tablets weights deviate from the average weight by more than the allowed percentage deviation and more deviate by more than twice the percentage shown. It was calculated on an electronic weighing balance.

c) Friability: The friability values of the tablets were determined using a Roche-type friabilator. Accurately weighed six tablets were placed in Roche friabilator and rotated at 25rpm for 4 min.

Percentage friability was calculated using the following equation.

$$\text{Friability} = ([w_0 - w] / w_0) \times 100$$

d) Assay: The content of drug was carried out by five randomly selected tablets of each formulation. The five tablets were grinded in mortar to get powder; this powder was dissolved in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer by sonication for 30 min and filtered through filter

paper. The drug content was analysed spectrophotometrically at 328 nm using UV spectrophotometer. Each measurement was carried out in triplicate and the average drug content was calculated.^[10,11]

e) Disintegration test: Six tablets were taken randomly from each batch and placed in USP disintegration apparatus baskets. Apparatus was run for 10 minutes and the basket was lift from the fluid, observe whether all of the tablets have disintegrated.

f) Dissolution test of Deferasirox tablets: Drug release from Deferasirox tablets was determined by using dissolution test United States Pharmacopoeia (USP) 24 type II (paddle). The parameters used for performing the dissolution were pH 6.8 phosphate buffer as the dissolution medium of quantity 500ml. the whole study is being carried out at a temperature of 37°C and at speed of 50 rpm.

5 ml aliquots of dissolution media were withdrawn each time at suitable time intervals (5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 minutes.) and replaced with fresh medium.

After withdrawing, samples were filtered and analyzed after appropriate dilution by UV Spectrophotometer. The concentration was calculated using standard calibration curve.^[12]

Drug-Excipients compatibility studies: Drug Excipients compatibility studies were carried out by mixing the drug with various excipients in different proportions (in 1:1 ratio were prepared to have maximum likelihood interaction between them) was placed in a vial, and closed with rubber stopper and sealed properly.^[13,14]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Determination of λ max: The Prepared stock solution was scanned between 200-400 nm to determine the absorption maxima. It was found to be 328 nm.

Calibration curve of Deferasirox: The standard curve of Deferasirox was obtained and good correlation was obtained with R^2 value of 0.999 the medium selected was pH 6.8 phosphate buffer.

Table 2: Standard graph values of Deferasirox at 328nm in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
0	0
5	0.126
10	0.241
15	0.348
20	0.459
25	0.577

Fig 1: Standard curve of Deferasirox

Drug-Excipient compatibility studies by FTIR Studies:

Deferasirox was mixed with various proportions of excipients showed no colour change at the end of two months, providing no drug excipient interactions.

Fig 2: FTIR spectra of pure drug

Fig 3: FTIR spectra of optimized formulation

Table 3: Physical properties of precompression blend

Formulation code	Bulk density (gm/cm ³)	Tapped density (gm/cm ³)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose (Θ)
F1	0.45 ± 0.18	0.56 ± 0.38	9.18 ± 0.16	1.05 ± 0.38	27.4 ± 0.59
F2	0.44 ± 0.43	0.58 ± 0.87	11.25 ± 0.84	1.12 ± 0.57	29.1 ± 0.54
F3	0.48 ± 0.51	0.53 ± 0.25	7.12 ± 0.73	1.07 ± 0.31	25.9 ± 0.87
F4	0.41 ± 0.34	0.52 ± 0.64	8.61 ± 0.45	1.16 ± 0.45	27.4 ± 0.38
F5	0.49 ± 0.83	0.58 ± 0.82	11.56 ± 0.19	1.07 ± 0.76	25.8 ± 0.65
F6	0.51 ± 0.52	0.51 ± 0.36	9.43 ± 0.57	1.12 ± 0.42	27.1 ± 0.18
F7	0.48 ± 0.48	0.58 ± 0.17	9.72 ± 0.16	1.06 ± 0.59	26.5 ± 0.46
F8	0.42 ± 0.14	0.54 ± 0.25	12.28 ± 0.95	1.03 ± 0.34	28.3 ± 0.57
F9	0.49 ± 0.87	0.51 ± 0.41	8.19 ± 0.39	1.15 ± 0.83	28.7 ± 0.92
F10	0.43 ± 0.56	0.56 ± 0.59	7.27 ± 0.55	1.09 ± 0.27	25.1 ± 0.49
F11	0.45 ± 0.42	0.54 ± 0.47	10.46 ± 0.47	1.12 ± 0.31	27.5 ± 0.35
F12	0.44 ± 0.98	0.51 ± 0.28	9.35 ± 0.28	1.16 ± 0.56	29.9 ± 0.47

All the values represent n=3

EVALUATION OF TABLETS:

Physical evaluation of Deferasirox Immediate release tablets:

Table 4: Physical evaluation of Deferasirox

Formulation code	Wt. variation (mg)	Thickness (cm)	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Content uniformity (%)
F1	100.75	2.86	3.27	0.86	100.74
F2	99.18	2.37	3.82	0.57	99.45
F3	100.86	2.52	3.17	0.67	99.14
F4	100.49	2.76	3.47	0.55	99.19
F5	100.15	2.39	3.55	0.68	99.85
F6	99.32	2.51	3.87	0.59	100.33
F7	100.46	2.62	3.41	0.67	98.58
F8	100.28	2.27	3.51	0.86	99.17
F9	101.13	2.35	3.25	0.63	99.62
F10	99.54	2.28	3.26	0.72	98.18
F11	100.85	2.41	3.12	0.51	100.54
F12	100.37	2.83	3.67	0.78	99.19

In-vitro release studies: The drug release rate from tablets was studied using the USP type II dissolution test apparatus. The dissolution medium was 500 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer at 50 rpm at a temperature of 37±0.5°C. Samples of 5 ml were collected at different time intervals up to 45 minutes and has analysed after appropriate dilution by using UV spectrophotometer .at 328nm.

Table 5: In-vitro dissolution data for formulation F1-F4

TIME (Mins)	% DRUG RELEASE			
	F-1	F-2	F-3	F-4
0	0	0	0	0
5	20.26	21.55	33.45	29.27
10	24.13	33.79	43.22	35.16
15	44.18	46.14	56.18	44.23
20	68.45	62.16	67.29	58.38
25	74.29	78.87	83.49	76.12
30	78.73	83.41	88.26	88.53
45	84.57	88.33	93.25	95.49

Fig 4: In-vitro dissolution data for formulation F1-F4

Table 6: *In-vitro* dissolution data for formulations F5-F8

TIME (Mins)	% DRUG RELEASE			
	F-5	F-6	F-7	F-8
0	0	0	0	0
5	24.87	32.42	31.86	26.76
10	34.36	42.53	42.57	37.51
15	48.19	53.68	54.65	45.16
20	58.37	64.35	76.28	66.55
25	68.18	69.92	83.79	71.14
30	74.35	72.45	87.46	83.56
45	77.76	85.36	99.94	92.67

Fig 5: *In-vitro* dissolution data for formulations F5-F8Table 7: *In-vitro* dissolution data for formulations F9-F12

TIME (Mins)	% DRUG RELEASE			
	F-9	F-10	F-11	F-12
0	0	0	0	0
5	24.72	21.62	19.27	14.26
10	39.87	28.10	28.51	35.51
15	45.61	46.81	39.35	39.53
20	56.28	59.19	46.36	48.93
25	79.43	66.38	59.18	57.16
30	88.63	77.87	66.34	62.35
45	95.74	85.46	71.82	69.57

Fig 6: *In-vitro* dissolution data for formulations F9-F12

CONCLUSION:

- The standard curve of Deferasirox was obtained and good correlation was obtained with R^2 value of 0.999. The medium selected was pH 6.8 phosphate buffer.
- Deferasirox was mixed with various proportions of excipients showed no colour change at the end of 2 months, proving no drug-excipient interactions.
- The pre-compression blend of Deferasirox immediate release tablets using super disintegrants were characterized with respect to angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index and Hausner's ratio. The precompression blend of all batches indicating good to fair flowability and compressibility.
- Immediate release tablets were prepared with various concentrations of polymers and were compressed into tablets.
- The formulated tablets were evaluated for various quality control parameters. The tablets were passed all the tests.
- The formulations (F-7) prepared with Sodium Starch glycolate (SSG) polymer showed drug release in increasing order. The formulation (F-7) containing drug and Sodium Starch glycolate (SSG) showed good drug release at 30 mg concentration.
- Among all the formulations F-7 formulation containing drug and Sodium Starch glycolate (30 mg concentration) showed maximum and good result that is 99.94% drug release in 45mins. Hence from dissolution data it was evident that F7 formulation is the better formulation.

REFERENCES:

1. Snehal B. Kulkarni, M. M. Bari, S. D. Barhate, Ashutosh Tripathi. Formulation and Evaluation of Immediate Release Tablet of Efavirenz by Micellar Solubilization Technique. Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 2019; 9(1): 12-18.
2. Sonali S. Jaiswal, Shashikant D. Barhate. Formulation Optimization and Evaluation of Immediate Release Tablet of Telmisartan. Asian Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2019; 9(3):167-173.
3. Abhishek Kumar Singh, Kasif Shakeel. Formulation and Evaluation of Immediate Release Tablets of Etizolam. Research Journal of Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms and Technology, 2021; 13(4): 281-284.
4. B. V. Ramana, T. E. G. K. Murthy. Formulation and Evaluation of Immediate Release Tablets Of Pioglitazone Hydrochloride by Employing Modified Superdisintegrants. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, 2018; 9(6): 2335-2346.
5. Hitesh P. Patel, Preeti Karwa, Rama Bukka, Nitesh J. Patel. Formulation and Evaluation of Immediate Release Tablets of Zolpidem Tartrate by Direct Compression. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research, 2011; 7 (2): 80-85.
6. Seemanchala R. Formulation & optimization of immediate release telmisartan tablets using full factorial design. International journals & applied pharmaceuticals, 2011; 3: 20-21.
7. Susijit Sahoo, B.Mishra, P.IK. Biswal, Omprakash Panda, Santosh Kumar Mahapatra, Goutam Kumar Jana. Fast Dissolving Tablet: As A Potential Drug Delivery System. Drug Invention Today, 2010; (2), 130-133.
8. Pani Nihar Ranjan. Optimization and Formulation of Immediate Release Tablet of Nateglinide by Using Factorial Design. International Journal of Pharm Tech Research, 2010; 2(3):1978- 1984.
9. Jahan Nur Rahman Hazarika, Pulak Deb. Formulation evaluation and optimization of immediate release tablet of Aceclofenac by direct compression method. Int J Curr Pharm Res, 2017; 9(3): 118-122.
10. Remya P.N, Saraswathi.T.S, Sangeetha.S , Damodharan N , Kavitha.R. Formulation and Evaluation of Immediate Release Tablets of Acyclovir. J. Pharm. Sci. & Res, 2016; 8(11): 1258-1261.
11. S. Jayani, D. Pandey, M. S. Charde. Formulation and evaluation of immediate release tablets of Metformin hydrochloride on laboratory scale. IJAPA, 2012; 2 (2): 30-33.
12. Abhijit Sonje, Arun Yadav, A. Chandra, D. A. Jain. Formulation and evaluation of immediate release tablet of Antihypertensive drugs according to BCS system. International Journal of Therapeutic Applications. 2012; 7: 18-24.
13. Gowtham.M, Vasanti.S, Rohan.RD, Ashwath.N, Paridhavi.M. Formulation and evaluation of immediate release folic acid tablets. Der Pharmacia Lettre, 2011; 3 (6): 157-162.
14. B.G.Shiyani, R.B.Dholakiya, B.V.Akbari, D.J.Lodhiya, G.K.Ramani. Development and evaluation of novel immediate release tablets of Metoclopramide HCl by direct compression using treated gellan gum as a disintegration-accelerating agent. Journal of Pharmacy Research, 2009; 2(9): 1460-1464.